

Spectroscopic Studies of some Benzilic Hydrazone Derivatives

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The interest in studying arylidene hydrazones¹ arises from their antituberculous effect² and usefulness as quantitative analytical reagents³. The spectral behaviour of some aryl hydrazones had been studied by Issa *et al.*⁴.

The present article deals with the spectral study of some of benzilic hydrazones (1-18) by using uv, ir and nmr spectroscopy. The electronic spectra in organic solvents of different polarities are studied and discussed. The various solvent parameters are considered.

X = H (1), *o*-OH (2), *m*-OH (3), *p*-OH (4), 2,4-(OH)₂ (5), 2-OH naph. (6), *o*-Cl (7), *m*-Cl (8), *p*-Cl (9), *m*-Br (10), *o*-NO₂ (11), *m*-NO₂ (12), *p*-NO₂ (13), *p*-N(CH₃)₂ (14), *o*-OCH₃ (15), *p*-OCH₃ (16), 3,4-(OCH₃)₂ (17), *p*-CH₃ (18).

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra in ethanol and cyclohexane :

Band assignment : The electronic spectra of the benzilic hydrazones (1-18) show five bands (A-E) (Table 1). Band-A lying within the range 203–237 nm is attributed to the medium energy $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the aromatic ring corresponding to the electronic state (¹L_a-¹A)⁵. Band-B (216–279 nm) can be assigned to the low energy $\pi-\pi^*$ (¹L_b-¹A)⁶. Band-C (260–296 nm) may be attributed to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition within the C=O group while band-D (281–326 nm) corresponds to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the C=N group. Band-E (298–372 nm) is sensitive to the nature of the substituent (x). This band is assigned to an electronic transition involving charge transfer (CT) interaction within the whole molecule. The CT character of the band can be supported by calculating the E_{CT} values using the equation⁷,

$$E_{CT} = I_p - (E_A + C)$$

considering the I_p of OH group as donor part (8.51 eV)⁸, the electron affinity E_A of the C=O group as the acceptor part (-1.5 eV)⁹ and the coulombic force (C) between the electron transferred and positive hole left behind (5.6 eV). The E_{CT} values obtained using the above equation for the hydrazones amount to 4.41 eV, whereas those obtained practically using the relation,

TABLE I—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS OF BENZILIC HYDRAZONE DERIVATIVES IN ETHANOL

Compd. no.	Band-A ¹ L _a - ¹ A		Band-B ¹ L _b - ¹ A		Band-C $\pi-\pi^*$ (C=O)		Band-D $\pi-\pi^*$ (C=N)		Band-E CT	
	λ nm	$\epsilon \times 10^{-4}$	λ nm	$\epsilon \times 10^{-4}$	λ nm	$\epsilon \times 10^{-4}$	λ nm	$\epsilon \times 10^{-4}$	λ nm	$\epsilon \times 10^{-4}$
1	215	2.27	—	—	282	2.43	290	2.45	302	1.64
2	224	2.36	279	2.40	279	2.40	324	1.30	372	0.95
3	217	3.04	—	—	284	2.34	295	2.08	320	1.00
4	220	2.40	—	—	296	2.72	308	2.90	319	2.42
5	—	—	242	1.26	296	1.48	326	1.74	366	2.45
6	237	2.98	—	—	286	0.48	320	1.28	356	2.45
7	223	2.08	—	—	284	2.56	292	2.70	312	1.80
8	210	3.04	—	—	290	2.36	308	1.48	328	0.22
9	218	2.60	—	—	296	3.08	308	2.42	330	0.34
10	—	—	—	—	290	2.68	310	1.68	330	0.36
11	—	—	264	1.70	280	1.62	—	—	334	0.80
12	—	—	258	0.26	—	—	—	—	334	0.52
13	—	—	248	1.04	—	—	—	—	336	2.52
14	—	—	236	1.34	—	—	—	—	310	1.68
15	—	—	270	1.22	282	1.48	292	1.38	350	1.20
16	220	2.38	—	—	296	2.84	308	3.10	320	3.76
17	224	1.88	—	—	292	2.10	326	2.22	356	1.50
18	220	2.48	—	—	294	2.82	308	2.24	322	0.50

$$E_{CT} = 1239.9/\lambda_{CT} \text{ (nm)} \text{ eV}$$

amount to 3.69–4.16 eV, showing a satisfactory agreement.

Substituent effect: The CT band displays a marked shift with changed nature and position of the substituent on the arylidene ring. The CT band is shifted to longer wavelength as the acceptor character of the substituent on the phenyl ring increases. The plots of λ_{max} as a function of the Hammett constant (σ_x), are satisfactory linear relations indicating that the position of the CT band is directly affected by the nature of the substituent hence the charge density on the arylidene ring. This reveals the validity of the Hammett linear free energy relation,

$$\lambda_x = \lambda_H \pm \rho\sigma_x$$

The data for such regression are $\lambda_H = 323 \text{ nm}$, r (correlation coefficient) = 0.97, $\rho = 15.2$ and s (standard deviation) = 8.41 for ethanol, and $\lambda_H = 317 \text{ nm}$, $r = 0.96$, $\rho = 21.1$ and $s = 3.48$ for cyclohexane.

Ir spectra :

The infrared spectra of the benzilic hydrazone derivatives (**1-18**) exhibit a bands at 3 477–3 320 (OH) and 3 276–3 194 cm^{-1} (NH). The low frequencies of both ν_{OH} and ν_{NH} can be ascribed to the presence of an intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The bands of aliphatic ν_{C-H} of azomethine linkage are observed at 3 020–2 908 cm^{-1} while those of the ν_{C-H} of the aromatic rings¹⁰ at 3 063–3 020 cm^{-1} . The compounds reveal bands at 1 687–1 660 (C=O) and 1 651–1 620 cm^{-1} (C=N)¹¹. They also exhibit a single band within the range 1 620–1 572 cm^{-1} corresponding to the in-plane deformation of the NH group (amide-II). Compounds containing the NO₂ group (**11-13**) show bands due to the asymmetric stretching vibration of NO₂ group at 1 596–1 564 cm^{-1} . The stretching vibration of the C–N group¹² (amide-III) leads to a medium band or shoulder at 1 275–1 241 cm^{-1} . On the other hand, the bands at 1 189–1 161 cm^{-1} correspond to the stretching mode of N–N group. Two medium bands appear in the range 1 251–1 220 cm^{-1} for the various deformation modes of the methyl group and at 1 029–1 019 cm^{-1} for the symmetric stretching mode of benzilic hydrazones (**15-17**). The spectra **11-13** reveal bands due to the symmetrical stretching of the NO₂ group at 1 345–1 340 cm^{-1} . The bands at 1 084–1 048 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the C–H in-plane deformation. The *para*-disubstituted benzylidene rings of the hydrazones under investigation show two bands at 837–815 cm^{-1} due to out-of-plane bending vibration of two adjacent H-atoms¹³. The bands at 679–647 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the chloro-substituted benzilic hydrazones (**7-9**) can be assigned to the C–Cl stretching vibration. The band at 646 cm^{-1} of **10** is assigned to the C–Br stretching vibration. The position of the bands due to the hydrazone part is affected by changing the nature of the substituent on the arylidene ring. The results indicate that the position of most of the bands is influenced by changes in the electronic character of the substituent on the benzylidene ring. The

plot of the wavenumber of the ν_{OH} , ν_{NH} , ν_{CH} , $\nu_{C=O}$, $\nu_{C=N}$, $\nu_{N=N}$, ν_{C-N} and δ_{NH} bands as a function of the σ -Hammett constants are satisfactory linear relations. This indicates the validity of the Hammett equation,

$$\nu_x = \nu_H + \rho\sigma_x$$

The data for such regressions are summarised in Table 2. The C=N bands are generally shifted to higher wavenumbers with electron acceptor substituent and to lower values with increasing donor character of the substituent.

TABLE 2—STATISTICAL RESULTS FOR BENZILIC HYDRAZONE DERIVATIVE FROM IR DATA

	ν_H	r	ρ	s
ν_{OH}	3 333	0.90	10.48	2 83
ν_{NH}	3 242	0.90	10.22	3 02
ν_{CH}	2 930	0.99	27.81	1.13
$\nu_{C=O}$	1 663	0.99	8.79	0.56
$\nu_{C=N}$	1 646	1.00	2 80	4.65
δ_{NH}	1 609	1.00	13 63	0.51
ν_{C-N}	1 268	0.99	7 23	0.49
ν_{N-N}	1 171	0.98	6 28	0.77

¹H nmr spectra :

The ¹H nmr spectra of the benzilic hydrazone derivatives **1**, **2**, **9**, **13**, **14**, **16** and **18** were recorded. The spectra in comparison to the corresponding hydrazide, show the disappearance of NH₂ group signals, while that of the NH protons are shifted up field to the range δ 10.40–11.80 as a result of the deshielding effect of HC=N group as well as increased tendency to keto-enol tautomerism and strengthening of hydrogen bonding. The proton of azomethine group (CH=N) leads to a sharp signal near δ 8.50–8.80 which is still observed after the addition of D₂O. The multi-signals at δ 6.57–8.40 ppm are characteristic of the aromatic protons. On deuteration, the signals observed at δ 10.40 (δ_{NH}) 7.10 (δ_{OH} aliphatic) and 11.00 (*o*-OH phenolic in case of compound **2**) disappear. Compound **14** shows a sharp signal at δ 3.00 which is characteristic of protons of the N(CH₃)₂ group. The sharp signal appears at δ 3.80 of **16** is characteristic of the protons of the OCH₃ group. Similarly, **18** shows a sharp signal at δ 2.40 which is characteristic of the protons of the CH₃ group. The shift of the NH, CH_(CH=N) and OH_{alc} signals with the change of the substituent (x) reveals that the changes in the electron shielding of the NH, CH_(CH=N) and OH_{alc} groups are parallel to the changes in electron density of the azomethine nitrogen which are caused by the varied electronic character of the substituent (x) on the arylidene ring.

Experimental

All chemicals were pure grade (B.D.H.). They included methyl ester of benzilic acid, hydrazine hydrate, benzaldehyde and some of its derivatives. The organic solvents used were either spectroscopic pure or purified by the recommended methods¹⁴ and tested for their spectral

purity. The electronic spectra (ethanol) were scanned on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 5 spectrophotometer, infrared spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer and proton-nmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Varian EM 360 L spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

The benzilic hydrazones (1-18) : The arylidene derivatives of benzilic hydrazides were prepared by condensation of the corresponding hydrazide (0.1 mol) with the appropriate aromatic aldehyde (0.1 mol) in ethanol as a solvent. After refluxing the mixture for 1-4 h on a water-bath, the resulting hydrazones were crystallised from ethanol and dried in a desiccator over silica gel : **1**, m.p. 149-50°; **2**, 211-12°; **3**, 242-44°; **4**, 258-60°; **5**, 261-62°; **6**, 265-67°; **7**, 241-42°; **8**, 209-10°; **9**, 220-21°; **10**, 293-94°; **11**, 269-70°; **12**, 219°; **13**, 218°; **14**, 232-33°; **15**, 137-38°; **16**, 173-74°; **17**, 167-68°; **18**, 216-17°. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

All compounds (**1-18**) were dissolved in ethanol to prepare 10^{-3} M stock solutions and lower concentrations were obtained by accurate dilution. Due to the low solubility of the compounds in cyclohexane, saturated solutions were first prepared, left to attain equilibrium and the insoluble portion was then filtered off so as to obtain a clear solution. The resulting solutions were used as such or diluted to give a measurable absorption spectra.

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